

BEFORE THE PUBLIC UTILITIES COMMISSION OF THE STATE OF COLORADO

DOCKET NO. 11A-869E

IN THE MATTER OF THE APPLICATION OF PUBLIC SERVICE COMPANY OF
COLORADO FOR APPROVAL OF ITS 2011 ELECTRIC RESOURCE PLAN

ANSWER TESTIMONY OF

DR. ZANE SELVANS

JUNE 4, 2012

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1 **INTRODUCTION**

2
3 **Q: PLEASE STATE YOUR NAME AND PLACE OF EMPLOYMENT.**

4 A: My name is Zane A. Selvans. I currently work as an independent consultant, doing business
5 as Selvans Analytics, LLC.

6
7 **Q: ON WHOSE BEHALF ARE YOU TESTIFYING?**

8 A: I am testifying on behalf of Ms. Glustrom, a party in this docket.

9
10 **Q: PLEASE DESCRIBE YOUR EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND AND**
11 **QUALIFICATIONS**

12 A: I have a B.S. in Engineering and Applied Science from the California Institute of Technology
13 (Caltech) and a PhD in Geological Sciences from the University of Colorado at Boulder. I am the
14 Principal Scientist at Selvans Analytics, LLC and I undertake data analyses on a variety of
15 subjects including U.S. coal supply and cost issues. A summary of my qualifications is included
16 in Attachment A at the end of this document.

17 **SUMMARY**

18 **Q: PLEASE PROVIDE A SUMMARY OF YOUR TESTIMONY AND**
19 **RECOMMENDATIONS**

20 **A:** The purpose of my testimony is to discuss PSCo’s coal supply and cost estimates, as well as
21 relevant factors that might affect their validity going forward, and to recommend actions that
22 may help insulate the Colorado rate payers against unforeseen price increases. In particular:

- 1 • PRB coal is plentiful, but that does not necessarily mean it will remain cheap for the next
2 30 years. Predicting future prices is very difficult, and even with the work done by the
3 USGS and the John T. Boyd report, it is very worthwhile to monitor market conditions as
4 they evolve.
- 5 • Factors which may affect future Powder River Basin (PRB) coal production costs
6 include:
- 7 ○ More aggressive enforcement of the SEC’s reserve reporting regulations, which
8 could influence public and investor perceptions of coal’s abundance as a fuel,
9 relative to natural gas.
 - 10 ○ Persistently high or increasing oil prices will in turn increase both coal production
11 and transportation costs.
 - 12 ○ Increasing coal production costs will in turn increase the cost of local electricity
13 generation, which will affect the cost of operating electrically powered excavation
14 machinery.
 - 15 ○ Greater competition among mining companies for federal resources within the
16 PRB leasing areas may increase the cost of acquiring new mining tracts.
 - 17 ○ Stripping ratios may not increase smoothly as mining proceeds westward in the
18 Gillette Coalfield, leading to uneven increases in production costs.
 - 19 ○ Large capital investments may be required in the rail sector to accommodate
20 increasing freight volumes, partly due to increased coal production within the
21 PRB.

22 My recommendations for the Colorado PUC are as follows:

- 1 • The Colorado PUC should compile a report, no less than annually, detailing actual coal
2 production costs, and delivered coal costs and compare them with the estimates provided
3 by PSCo in the resource plan.
- 4 • Future coal production cost estimates, along the lines of those produced by the USGS in
5 OFR 2008-1202 and the John T. Boyd report, should be performed in conjunction with
6 all subsequent resource plans which incorporate a significant amount of coal-based
7 generation, to ensure that the resource planning process is using up-to-date market
8 information.
- 9 • In the event that realized fuel costs diverge significantly and persistently from the
10 estimates provided in the ERP, the PUC should remain open to the possibility of new
11 generation resources competing directly with existing resources in future resource plans,
12 should that turn out to be economically advantageous.

13

14 XCEL'S COAL SUPPLY AND COST TESTIMONY

15 Q: WHAT INFORMATION HAS XCEL PROVIDED ON COAL COST AND SUPPLY?

16 A: In Volume 2 of Xcel's 2011 Resource Plan they have stated that "Information from EIA and
17 USGS indicated that demand [for Powder River Basin Coal] over the next 30 years would be
18 approximately 17 billion tons, while the coal resource in the PRB exceeded 140 billion tons."

19 They also noted that "the area that supplies coal to Pawnee and Comanche [the Gillette coal
20 field] is estimated to contain 24-34 billion tons of economically recoverable coal during the next
21 30 years." (2011 Xcel ERP vol. 2 p. 2-28). Based on the work of their consultant, the John T.

22 Boyd Company, Xcel believes that 20.5 billion tons of the economically extractable coal within

1 the Gillette coal field are mineable from existing or planned mining operations (as summarized in
2 Table 2.2-2, Xcel ERP vol. 2 p. 2-29). Additionally, the work of the John T. Boyd Company
3 indicated to Xcel that in real (inflation adjusted) terms, the Gillette coal field production costs
4 could reasonably be expected to increase from about \$10/ton today to \$15/ton in 2040, due
5 primarily to the need to access increasingly deeply buried coal reserves. Xcel's position is that
6 there exists sufficient, reasonably priced Powder River Basin coal to fuel the Pawnee and
7 Comanche plants for the next 30 years.

8 On page 2-265 of Volume 2 of their proposed Resource Plan, Xcel describes the general
9 input parameters which they use to generate their coal price forecast, i.e. "the current contract
10 volumes and prices combined with current estimates of required spot volumes and prices." But
11 they do not give a specific price forecast, indicating instead that this information will be updated
12 for the Phase 2 evaluation of the 2011 ERP.

13

14 **Q: HAVE YOU REVIEWED THE JOHN T. BOYD REPORT REFERRED TO BY**
15 **XCEL, AND IF SO WHAT GENERAL CONCERNS DO YOU HAVE ABOUT THAT**
16 **STUDY?**

17 **A:** Yes. The John T. Boyd report was provided to the parties in discovery and I have reviewed
18 that report. With respect to the geological setting and fundamental production cost constraints
19 the Boyd report is generally consistent with the recent US Geological Survey assessment of the
20 Gillette coal field (USGS OFR 2008-1202), which to my knowledge represents the best
21 publically available independent assessment of the region's resources. The John T. Boyd study
22 appears to imply a 20-35% higher estimate of coal production costs in 2040 than the USGS
23 study. The reasons for that difference are not immediately obvious, but may reflect either a

1 higher rate of return for the mining companies or different assumptions about the cost of
2 commodity inputs to the mining process, such as diesel fuel.

3 My concerns regarding the Boyd study might also reasonably apply to the USGS study,
4 and generally reflect inherent uncertainties in the prediction of future production costs due either
5 to intrinsic cost escalations or changes to the regulatory environment. They are summarized
6 here:

- 7 • While mining will generally proceed from easily accessible reserves to more deeply
8 buried, costly reserves, this progression is not always continuous. Mining operations in
9 the eastern PRB will in some cases be required to develop areas of higher stripping ratios
10 first as they progress westward, following the coal seams downward toward areas of
11 lower stripping ratios.
- 12 • Should the Powder River Basin be re-certified as a “Coal Producing Region” by the
13 federal government, the current Lease By Application (LBA) process used by the BLM to
14 allocate leases in the Powder River Basin may be replaced by a more competitive bidding
15 process, increasing the cost of acquiring new coal reserves.
- 16 • The SEC may more stringently enforce its reserve reporting rules. This would bring coal
17 reserve reporting into line with other fossil fuels, especially natural gas. This may
18 significantly alter investor and public perception of coal’s relative abundance and long-
19 term viability as a fuel.
- 20 • Persistently high or rising oil prices may result in higher than expected production and
21 transportation costs, as diesel fuel represents a significant proportion of both long-
22 distance rail freight and truck-and-shovel excavation costs.

- 1 • Increasing coal production costs associated with higher stripping ratios will in turn
2 increase the cost of generating electricity used to run electrically powered excavation
3 machinery.
- 4 • Large capital investments in rail infrastructure nationwide may be required to alleviate
5 cargo congestion as coal shipping volumes increase, increasing rail freight rates.

6
7 I will discuss each of these in further detail below and provide additional information regarding
8 U.S. coal supplies, with a particular emphasis on the Powder River Basin, which was the focus of
9 the John T. Boyd study and is the source of coal for Xcel’s 505 MW Pawnee coal plant in Brush,
10 Colorado (NE of Denver) and the 1160 MW Xcel share of the Comanche coal plants in Pueblo,
11 Colorado (about 100 miles south of Denver.)

12
13 **Q: WHAT IS YOUR GENERAL REACTION TO XCEL’S COAL COST AND SUPPLY**
14 **TESTIMONY?**

15 A: My general reaction to Xcel’s coal supply testimony is that it accurately portrays the
16 geological realities of Powder River Basin coal production, but that it may underplay the
17 potential for legal, regulatory, and energy market changes over the coming several decades.

18 **COAL RESOURCES VS. COAL RESERVES**

19
20 **Q: WHAT IS THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN COAL RESOURCES AND RESERVES?**

21 A: In the nomenclature of coal geology, the word “resources” refers to the quantity of original
22 rock in the ground. Resources may or may not be technically extractable given the current state

1 of mining technology. When they are technically extractable, they may still be unavailable due
2 to other mining restrictions, such as the presence of nearby infrastructure, human habitation,
3 protected habitat, water resources, or historic sites that cannot be re-located, either legally or
4 economically. Additionally, even when a resource is available for mining, it is generally the case
5 that only a fraction of the original rock in place may actually be extracted. In room-and-pillar
6 mining, the pillars are generally left behind. In surface strip mining as practiced generally in the
7 Powder River Basin, a thin layer of coal at the top and the bottom of the bed being mined is
8 typically left in place or discarded to avoid contamination from the surrounding sediment.
9 Perhaps most importantly, even the practically extractable portion of the original resource may
10 only be available at a production cost that would make the mining operation uneconomic at
11 prevailing market prices.

12 “Reserves” are the portion of existing resources in the ground that can be technically,
13 legally, and economically extracted, given current technology, regulations, and market prices
14 (see SEC Industry Guide 7). In the regulatory language of the SEC resources may either be
15 “proven” (measured) or “probable” (indicated). If reserves are proven, this means that their
16 quantity and extent are very well understood based on a large number of closely spaced existing
17 outcrops, workings or drill holes, and that their grade and/or quality are well constrained based
18 on detailed and extensive sampling. Probable reserves are less assured, usually because of
19 greater spacing between sites of measurement.

20

21 **Q: WHY IS THE DISTINCTION BETWEEN RESOURCES AND RESERVES**
22 **IMPORTANT IN THE CONTEXT OF LONG-TERM UTILITY RESOURCE**
23 **PLANNING?**

1 **A:** The distinction between resources and reserves is important because often the resources in the
2 ground far exceed the reserves that can be produced economically, but it has historically been
3 common for both the coal industry and the US Energy Information Administration (EIA) to
4 publish estimates of resources in place, or technically accessible resources, rather than
5 economically accessible reserves. This stands in contrast to standard practice in the oil and
6 natural gas industries, which have generally been required to report conservative reserve
7 estimates. If coal and natural gas are seen as substitutable for each other as fuels for potential
8 electrical generation, or if we are to consider liquid hydrocarbon fuels produced from coal as a
9 potential substitute for high cost imported oil, then it is important that we compare the reserve
10 estimates for all of these fuels fairly. Comparing oil and gas *reserves* to coal *resources* will give
11 the impression that on a relative basis, coal is far more abundant than it actually is. (See e.g.
12 Grubert in *Energy Policy* Vol. 44, May 2012, Pages 174–184 for a more thorough exploration.)

13 **NATURE OF THE POWDER RIVER BASIN**

14
15 **Q: WHAT IS THE NATIONAL COAL RESOURCE ASSESSMENT AND WHAT**
16 **RELEVANCE DOES IT HAVE TO THESE PROCEEDINGS?**

17 **A:** In the year 2000 the United States Geological Survey initiated a program, called the National
18 Coal Resource Assessment (NCRA) to systematically characterize both coal resources
19 nationwide, and to estimate the fraction of those resources likely to be able to economically serve
20 the nation’s energy production needs. To my knowledge, it represents the most comprehensive,
21 independent, publically available assessment of both our coal resources and reserves. The
22 information compiled by the USGS in this work provides the foundation necessary for making a

1 fair comparison of economically producible coal reserves with reserve estimates in the oil and
2 natural gas industries.

3 Of particular interest to this proceeding is the USGS Open-File Report (OFR) 2008-1202
4 entitled “Assessment of Coal Geology, Resources, and Reserves in the Gillette Coalfield,
5 Powder River Basin, Wyoming”. With recent development of coal bed methane (CBM) and oil
6 in the Powder River Basin, a wealth of new drilling logs has become available, densely covering
7 a large portion of the Gillette Coalfield. The USGS compiled coal bed data from more than
8 10,000 well logs and correlated it across the entire region, providing the public an unprecedented
9 view into the subsurface geology of North America’s most prodigious coal producing province.

10 The Powder River Basin produces more than 40% of US coal (more than 400 million
11 tons per year) and about 90% of that production comes from the Gillette Coalfield in the
12 southern portion of the basin. While production in the Appalachian region has been flat or
13 declining in recent years, Wyoming coal production has been increasing steadily since the 1970s,
14 fuelling an ever larger proportion of our electrical generation.

15

16 **Q: CAN YOU GIVE US A GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE POWDER RIVER**
17 **BASIN COAL DEPOSITS, AND THE GILLETTE COALFIELD IN PARTICULAR?**

18 **A:** PRB coal is relatively young compared to Appalachian coal deposits, having been emplaced
19 during the Paleocene and Eocene epochs, between 40-60 million years ago. It has relatively low
20 energy density compared to eastern coals (7800-9700 btu/lb vs. 1100-14200 btu/lb), but is
21 desirable for electrical generation because of its extremely low sulfur content (0.2-0.8%).

22 The shape of the basin is an elongated, asymmetric bowl, with its long axis oriented
23 roughly NNW-SSE. The coal beds on the eastern margin of the basin dip shallowly to the west,

1 and the beds on the western margin dip steeply to the east. Surface flow washed away
2 significant portions of the originally emplaced coal deposits in the central portion of the basin at
3 some point in the past.

4 Within the Gillette Coalfield the Anderson and Canyon beds are the most economically
5 viable resources, containing a significant majority of the coal in the region with a stripping ratio
6 of less than 10:1. Further to the west the Smith coal bed becomes a significant resource, but it is
7 so deeply buried that the USGS considered it likely to remain uneconomic as a reserve.

8

9 **Q: WHAT IS A STRIPPING RATIO, AND WHY IS IT IMPORTANT IN THE**
10 **CONTEXT OF COAL PRODUCTION COSTS?**

11 **A:** The effective stripping ratio is the total volume of waste material divided by the total
12 recoverable tons of coal within a given area, down to a particular depth. Waste material consists
13 mostly of *overburden* (which overlies the resource of interest), *interburden* (non-coal material
14 which lies between two coal beds), and *parting* (thin layers of non-coal material within a coal
15 bed). In surface mining operations, the effective stripping ratio is a primary driver of production
16 costs.

17

18 **Q: WHAT ARE THE IMPLICATIONS OF THIS GEOLOGICAL SETTING FOR**
19 **FUTURE COAL PRODUCTION COSTS?**

20 **A:** Coal mines in the Gillette Coalfield have generally progressed from the eastern margin of the
21 deposit toward the west, following the coal beds as they dip down shallowly. On average this
22 has ensured that the coal with the lowest production costs has been produced first. As mining
23 progresses westward, the effective stripping ratio increases, which in turn increases production

1 costs per ton of coal recovered. Production costs set a hard price floor, beneath which it no
2 longer makes economic sense for companies to mine the coal.

3

4 **Q: HOW DO INCREASING STRIPPING RATIOS AND PRODUCTION COSTS**
5 **AFFECT THE ESTIMATION OF ECONOMICALLY RECOVERABLE RESERVES?**

6 **A:** Any estimate of economically recoverable reserves must necessarily be tied to a given market
7 price for the produced coal. Future market prices are much less predictable than many of the
8 other technical and legal restrictions which determine whether or not an in place resource
9 qualifies as a viable reserve. Instead of choosing a particular price and determining the quantity
10 of resources at that price, we can better understand the quantity of economically recoverable
11 reserves as a relationship between the quantity produced and the cost of production. Both the
12 Boyd Report commissioned by PSCo and the USGS' OFR 2008-1202 estimate this relationship
13 based on modeling of production costs, given the publically accessible information on the coal
14 resources in place. These estimates allow us to choose a hypothetical market price, and
15 determine what quantity of coal may be produced profitably at or below that price. How
16 production costs evolve with time will thus depend on the rate at which mining takes place. Both
17 Boyd and the USGS predicted relatively modest, continuous increases in production costs as the
18 surface mines progress into areas with increased stripping ratios.

19

20 **Q: GIVEN EXPECTATIONS OF DEMAND FOR PRB COAL IN THE COMING**
21 **SEVERAL DECADES, HOW MUCH SHOULD WE EXPECT PRODUCTION COSTS**
22 **TO INCREASE?**

1 **A:** The Boyd Report estimated price increases over time, given a model of demand for PRB coal
2 resulting in roughly 17 billion tons of coal being produced between now and 2040. They
3 concluded that in real (inflation adjusted) terms, it was likely that by 2040 production costs
4 would average ~\$15/ton, and that market sale prices would need to be in the \$17.50-\$20/ton
5 range (depending on heat content) to make the extraction of that coal economically viable at a
6 profit. This is a somewhat higher estimate of economically viable market prices than was
7 reported by the USGS in OFR 2008-1202. The USGS, rather than assuming a particular demand
8 curve, simply estimated the economically accessible reserves as a function of market sale price.
9 At 19 billion tons of cumulative production (Boyd’s 17 billion tons plus the ~2 billion tons
10 which were produced between 2008 and 2012), the 2008 USGS required market price estimate
11 was in the neighborhood of \$14.00/ton. This means the Boyd estimates represent a ~20-35%
12 increase in the expected market price floor in 2040 over the USGS estimates from 2008.

13

14 **Q: WHAT IS THE REASON THAT THE BOYD REPORT ESTIMATE OF FUTURE**
15 **PRODUCTION COSTS IS HIGHER THAN THE 2008 ESTIMATE PRODUCED BY**
16 **THE USGS?**

17 **A:** It is not immediately obvious from comparing the two reports what change in underlying
18 assumptions might have generated this difference. The USGS assumed an 8% rate of return for
19 the mining companies; Boyd may have assumed a higher rate of return. Actually realized
20 production costs in the time between the USGS work and the preparation of the Boyd report may
21 also have been higher than the USGS anticipated, leading Boyd to conclude higher production
22 costs were likely. For instance, Alpha Natural Resources reported in their Q1 2012 8K filing that
23 PRB production costs averaged \$10.96/ton, compared to \$9.66/ton in Q1 2011. Similarly Cloud

1 Peak Energy indicated in their year-end 2011 10K filing that PRB production costs had increased
2 to \$9.12/ton from \$8.57/ton the previous year, and cited an increase in diesel fuel and lubricant
3 costs as major drivers of the production cost increase. These production costs appear to be
4 somewhat greater than those projected by the USGS in their 2008 report.

5
6 **Q: HOW MUCH COAL IS LIKELY TO BE ULTIMATELY RECOVERED FROM THE**
7 **POWDER RIVER BASIN?**

8 **A:** There is no entirely straightforward way to answer this question. Clearly there are vast coal
9 *resources* available within the PRB, should we decide it is worth paying very high prices to
10 extract them, turning them into economically recoverable *reserves*. What market price we are
11 willing to pay in the end will be largely determined by the cost evolution of alternatives to the
12 burning of PRB coal, such as natural gas, wind, and solar based electricity generation as well as
13 cost-effective energy efficiency measures.

14 However, recently several researchers including Patzek and Croft (2010) and Rutledge
15 (2011) have developed variations on M. King Hubbert's model of natural resource extraction
16 rates to both global and regional coal production, in the hopes of determining what the ultimate
17 quantity recovered is likely to be. Hubbert's technique models resource extraction rates as a
18 normal (bell-shaped) curve in time, with low initial production, increasing as the industry and
19 resource assessment matures, and eventually declining as the economically accessible reserves
20 are depleted. Cumulative production numbers for mature coal producing regions such as the
21 United Kingdom, S. Korea and Japan, and France and Belgium are fairly well predicted by this
22 method, even when the analysis is performed from the point of view of an observer in the past,
23 with only a limited subset of the historical production data available. Using this method,

1 Rutledge estimates that the entire cumulative western US coal production is likely to amount to
2 45 billion tons, and that 90% of this cumulative production is likely to have taken place by the
3 year 2054. He also observes a common tendency of national coal reserve estimates to be
4 extremely optimistic initially, and revised downward sharply late in the life of a coal producing
5 region (see D. Rutledge “Estimating long-term world coal production with logit and probit
6 transforms” *International Journal of Coal Geology* 85 (2011) pp 23-33).

7 Whether or not this method of predicting ultimate production will prove applicable to the
8 Powder River Basin remains to be seen, but it seems worth paying attention to.

9 **FACTORS INFLUENCING PRB PRODUCTION COSTS**

10

11 **Q: WHAT FORESEEABLE PRODUCTION COST RISKS EXIST IN THE POWDER**
12 **RIVER BASIN?**

13 **A:** I see two main sources of potential coal production cost risk in the PRB. The first is intrinsic
14 costs relating to production – it may simply turn out to be more expensive than expected to
15 produce the coal. The second is the potential for changes in the regulatory environment. I will
16 summarize these below.

17 While the stripping ratio does in general increase as one proceeds westward across the
18 Gillette Coalfield, it is not a perfectly smooth progression. It may be necessary in some cases for
19 mining to pass through an area of higher stripping ratios to get to an area of lower stripping
20 ratios, resulting in temporarily elevated production costs. The inputs to coal production,
21 especially energy, may increase in cost more rapidly than predicted. Most truck and shovel
22 operations are powered by diesel fuel. Should oil prices remain high or rise significantly, that

1 energy input would place upward pressure on production costs. Draglines and some shovel
2 operations rely on locally generated coal-fired electricity. As the cost of producing the coal
3 increases due to increasing stripping ratios, the cost of that electricity will also increase.

4 Though it is not strictly a production cost, transportation of coal from the mine mouth to
5 the ultimate site of consumption is a large component of the end cost to the users of PRB coal,
6 due to the remoteness of the mining region. Even in Colorado the transportation costs from the
7 PRB are a significant fraction of the delivered cost. Because of this, increases in the cost of rail
8 freight rates will have a direct impact on coal costs. The further a market is from the site of
9 production, the greater this effect will be. As with coal production itself, rail transportation costs
10 are largely governed by fuel costs. Should diesel remain expensive or increase in price, it would
11 increase the cost of getting the coal to its end user.

12 Capital investment to alleviate rail congestion is another factor that may increase coal
13 transportation costs. The National Rail Freight Infrastructure Capacity and Investment Study
14 performed by Cambridge Systematics in 2007 indicated that up to \$148 billion worth of capital
15 investment would be required to accommodate expected rail freight volumes by the year 2035.
16 Should those investments be made, they would likely be passed through to rail freight customers,
17 including coal consumers.

18 Plausible changes to the regulatory environment that could result in increased production
19 costs include the re-certification of the Powder River Basin as a “coal producing region” by the
20 BLM, as proposed under US Senator Sanders (I-VT) “End Polluter Welfare Act”. Were the PRB
21 to be re-certified as a coal producing region, the current lease by application (LBA) process
22 which allows mining companies to design potential auction tracts might be replaced with a more
23 competitive system, attracting a larger pool of potential bidders to each auction, and increasing

1 the cost per ton of acquired federal coal resources. Even under the current LBA process, the cost
2 of acquiring rights to mine federal resources in the Gillette Coalfield has increased substantially.
3 According to BLM documents in 1995 resources within a tract of the Eagle Butte mine were sold
4 for the equivalent of \$0.11/ton, even with a very favorable stripping ratio of less than 1:1. In
5 contrast, in may of 2012 a tract within the Black Thunder mine sold for nearly \$1.35/ton of
6 resources, despite having a substantially less favorable stripping ratio of 4.2:1.

7 Another regulatory risk is a potential change in the way coal reserves are reported. Were
8 the SEC and the USGS to prevail in their efforts to get mining companies and the US EIA to
9 consistently report only economically accessible coal reserves, it might have a negative impact
10 on perception of coal's relative abundance as an energy source in the eyes of the public,
11 investors, and major coal customers.

12 In the event that public and investor perception of coal as a relatively cheap and abundant
13 long term fuel source were to waver, it might become more difficult or expensive to obtain the
14 long term project financing required to initiate production at new mines in the Gillette Coalfield.
15 In particular as both the USGS and Boyd reports point out, a large capital expenditure will be
16 required when the existing mines eventually reach the joint Union Pacific and BNSF rail line that
17 serves the mining region, as well as highway 59. Those pieces of infrastructure will either need
18 to be re-located, or a new box-cut will need to be initiated to the west of the rail line and
19 highway.

20 **RECOMMENDATIONS**

21

1 **Q: WHAT ACTIONS WOULD YOU RECOMMEND THE COLORADO PUC TAKE TO**
2 **MITIGATE PRODUCTION COST RISKS?**

3 **A:** Both the USGS OFR 2008-1202 report and the John T. Boyd report commissioned by PSCo
4 appear to be good faith efforts to understand likely future production scenarios for the Powder
5 River Basin. However, predicting future prices correctly is very difficult. The US EIA and
6 many energy industry analysts with vast resources at their disposal routinely fail to get prices
7 right even in the short term, much less on a time scale of several decades. For this reason –
8 without disparaging the above mentioned works at all – I strongly recommend that the Colorado
9 PUC keep itself informed as to how the costs estimated in those works compare with actual
10 production costs as they are reported annually or even quarterly by the companies working in the
11 Powder River Basin. In particular the PUC ought to:

- 12 • Compile a quarterly summary of the production costs in the PRB as reported by the major
13 mining companies in their SEC filings, and compare it to the estimates provided by
14 PSCo. Are they consistent with the USGS and Boyd projections? If not, why? Are the
15 differences likely to be transient or permanent?
- 16 • Monitor the BLM leasing process to see how the resource cost per ton changes over time,
17 and to see what the average stripping ratios are for the tracts being purchased to supply
18 fuel for the coming decades. Are they smoothly increasing? Are they consistent with the
19 projections?
- 20 • Watch the delivered fuel costs (\$/mmBTU) as reported by PSCo to the US EIA on form
21 923 at least annually. Are they consistent with the projections made in the ERP?

22 Ideally, the PUC would require an annual report from PSCo detailing the above information, but
23 it could also be easily compiled by staff from publicly accessible resources.

1 While the USGS and Boyd reports are useful, as market conditions evolve they will
2 become increasingly outdated. Similar work, estimating how the minimum economically viable
3 market price evolves as a function of the total amount of coal extracted from the PRB should be
4 conducted in concert with all future resource planning, to ensure that the estimates reflect actual
5 market conditions.

6 In the event that any of the above data indicates that coal costs are diverging significantly
7 and consistently from the estimates provided in the ERP, it would be preferable if Colorado rate
8 payers were able to opt out of the long term commitment to the fuel that PSCo is making on their
9 behalf. Currently rate payers assume all of the risk associated with fluctuations in fuel prices. If
10 coal costs were to escalate particularly dramatically, it is possible that even with the sunk capital
11 cost of the existing plants, it could be economically advantageous to allow other resources to
12 compete with existing generation facilities in future resource plans, or on a day to day
13 dispatching basis. This is especially true given presently depressed natural gas prices, but if the
14 cost of renewable generation continues dropping they may become competitive as well. The
15 PUC should remain open to this possibility.

16

17

CONCLUSION

18

19 **Q: WHAT CONCLUSIONS DO YOU BELIEVE THE COLORADO PUC SHOULD**
20 **REACH ABOUT FUTURE COAL COST AND SUPPLY ISSUES FOR XCEL'S**
21 **COLORADO PLANTS?**

22 **A:** The conclusions I believe the Colorado PUC should reach are as follows:

- 1 • PRB coal is plentiful, but that does not necessarily mean it will remain cheap for the next
2 30 years. Predicting future prices is very difficult, and even with the work done by the
3 USGS and the John T. Boyd report, it is very worthwhile to monitor market conditions as
4 they evolve.
- 5 • The Colorado PUC should compile a report, no less than annually, detailing actual coal
6 production costs, and delivered coal costs and compare them with the estimates provided
7 by PSCo in the resource plan.
- 8 • Future coal production cost estimates, along the lines of those produced by the USGS in
9 OFR 2008-1202 and the John T. Boyd report, should be performed in conjunction with
10 all subsequent resource plans which incorporate a significant amount of coal-based
11 generation, to ensure that the resource planning process is using up-to-date market
12 information.
- 13 • In the event that realized fuel costs diverge significantly and persistently from the
14 estimates provided in the ERP, the PUC should remain open to the possibility of new
15 generation resources competing directly with existing resources in future resource plans,
16 should that turn out to be economically advantageous.

17

18 **Q: DOES THIS CONCLUDE YOUR ANSWER TESTIMONY AT THIS TIME?**

19 A: Yes. Thank you.

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ATTACHMENT A

I received my BS in Engineering and Applied Science from the California Institute of Technology (Caltech) in 1998. After working for two years in the software industry I returned to Caltech as technical staff working with data from NASA’s Mars Global Surveyor mission, where I first became familiar with geographic information systems (GIS) software. After two years at Caltech, I came to the University of Colorado at Boulder to pursue a PhD in Geology. My research focused on computationally modeling the viscoelastic tidal response of icy satellites in the outer solar system, and on developing novel statistical methods for correlating mapped tectonic features with the modeled tides. I defended my dissertation “Time, Tides, and Tectonics on Icy Satellites” and received my PhD in the fall of 2009. Since that time I have been engaged in consulting on the economics and geology of energy.